

(Comparative Assessment of Teacher's- Quality- Assurance Technique and Student's- Attitude on ... Kilani, M. O. Et. al. 2025)

Comparative Assessment of Teachers- Quality- Assurance Technique and Students- Attitude On Performance in Geography among Selected Secondary Schools in Kogi State, Nigeria

KILANI, Muhammed Olakunle¹

Kilanimuhammed@fceodugbo.edu.ng
[+2388053140506](tel:+2388053140506)

IBRAHIM, Grace John¹

grace.john81@yahoo.com
[+2348167511128](tel:+2348167511128)

HASSAN, Hauwa²

Hashauwa44@gmail.com
[+2348036941219](tel:+2348036941219)

¹Department of Geography, Federal College of Education Odugbo, Benue State, Nigeria

²Department of Geography, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study focused on comparative assessment of teachers-quality-assurance technique and students-attitude on performance in geography among selected secondary schools in Kogi State, Nigeria. The objective of the study was to investigate how students' attitudes affect their academic performance and determined the influence of the variable such as gender, religion and academic qualification. One hundred Geography teachers were randomly selected from twenty senior secondary schools in the area: five teachers from each selected school. The instruments were validated by experts in Geography education, and their reliability was confirmed through Cronbach's Alpha ($\alpha = 0.78$ for Students' Attitude to Geography Questionnaire AGQ; $\alpha = 0.82$ for Teacher Quality Assessment). The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and Pearson Product Moment Correlation co-efficient. The result of the analysis shows that the attitudes of respondents toward Geography were generally positive. There was relationship between gender, religion and teaching qualification. However, there was no relationship between professional experience and gender, religion and teaching qualification. Based on the findings, the study therefore recommended that qualified teachers should be employed to teach Geography; Geography should be made as a compulsory subject for students in senior secondary school.

Keywords: Academic Performances, Attitudes, Geography, Gender and Religion

Introduction

The importance of teaching Geography in senior secondary school and in tertiary institution of various part of the world is inestimable. Geography does not only provide the ability for the student to get acquainted with their immediate and outside environment, but encompasses human interaction with available resources provided by nature. Geography is beyond a mere description of the earth. Bonnett and Littlefield (2023) describes Geography as a fundamental fascination, and a crucial method for understanding the way the world works. This attempts to describe and explain the world and its people. There are many obstacles in such an undertaking, but one of the beauties and most fundamental is how we can know about people from other part of the world. The increased mobility economies, people and information means the issues of "Knowing Others" has become a defining dilemma of the modern era. Harm de-Blij, (2021), emphasized the importance of Geography as the

(Comparative Assessment of Teacher's-Quality-Assurance Technique and Student's-Attitude on ... Kilani, M. O. Et. al. 2025)

understanding of global issues, geopolitics, environmental challenges, and cultural diversity. Geography was viewed as a key tool for making sense of our interconnected world. Akintade (2012), described Geography as wide and interesting subjects that bordered other subjects such as social studies, other environmental studies and encourages students to work hard by finding more learning and obtain a mastery of concept therein. As a science of the earth, Geography has continually played a substantial role in the general development of any serious committed nations for its effectiveness. Geography is being taught in schools to offer students a sound knowledge of their immediate environment and to develop the ability to understand and give well detail of natural occurrences (Falode et al., 2020).

In Nigerian educational system, the sole criteria of determining the quality of teachers and student's performance are through the public examinations such as the Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination, West Africa Examination and Council (WAEC), National Teacher Institute (NTI) and Nigerian Examination Council (NECO). Academic performance is often used as a measure of a student's knowledge, skills, and understanding of the subjects they are studying. It is a multifaceted concept that can be done through various means and indicators which could be achieved through the following ways depending on the evaluator. These are grades, test scores, class participation, project and presentation, attendance of the lesson, teacher evaluations, overall grade points (GPA), extracurricular activities, self-assessment, homework and assignment.

Shehzad and Aziz (2019), described academic performance as the degree of a student's accomplishment in a task given in the studies in order to know how far and how well the lesson was comprehended. The most well-known indicator of measuring academic performance is grades which reflect the student's score for their subjects and overall tenure. This academic performance plays a significant role on a student's educational and career opportunities.

The attitude of students has to do with the feelings, beliefs, and behaviors of the students towards their academic pursuit. Petty and Cacioppo (2020), opined that attitudes are formed and changed through two routes: the central route (where people carefully process information) and the peripheral route (where people rely on heuristics or shortcuts). The route taken depends on the motivation and ability of the individual. That is to say, this encompasses a range of emotions and perspectives, and it can greatly influence a student's academic performance and overall educational experience. Attitude of students to teaching and learning of subject from the elementary to the higher degree is one of the serious challenges for students any part of the world. It is observed that student tends to perform better or get good grades when they show a positive behavior towards a particular subject and vice versa. This can only be made reliable by observing the students' working habits in laboratory and workshops, participation in the tutorial classes, discussion and attitude towards assignment. Osuji and Chelule (2023) opined that students have positive attitude towards Geography but the performance in the subject maybe subjected to teacher's methodology and educational resources.

As far as Geography is concerned, it is the only subject that touches many other disciplines such as Biology, Agricultural science, Economics, Social studies, Physics among others. Foin (2009), captures Geography as a versatile, expressive, creative, problem-solving, practical, intellectual-stimulating

(Comparative Assessment of Teacher's-Quality-Assurance Technique and Student's-Attitude on ... Kilani, M. O. Et. al. 2025)

school subject. As earlier pointed out (Obasi 2010 and Aderogba 2012), the content of Geography syllabuses in Nigeria, as given by both WAEC (2014) and NECO (2014), have been grouped into Elements of Practical Geography (which covers Map Work); Physical Geography; Human Geography; Regional Geography of West Africa with particular emphasis on Nigeria; Geography of Africa; and Field Work with the aim and objectives of the subject similarly captured by the both examination bodies as to:

- i. Understand the concepts of different characters and the spatial relationship of the features on the earth surface;
- ii. Understand the concepts of man-environment relations, that is, to examine and explain the interaction of man with his physical and cultural environments;
- iii. Acquire the basic knowledge of the nature and functions of physical and human environments and understanding of their interrelationships in the resulting issues;
- iv. Organize and formulate principles according to acquired geographical concepts, and apply these principles to interpret and analyze spatial problems in the immediate and wider environment;
- v. Develop skills and techniques for accurate orderly and objective geographical investigations to be carried out both in the classroom and in the environment.

Statement of the Research Problem

It was observed that poor performance in Geography among the senior secondary students has resulted to massive dropping for other subject; such as Literature in English, History and Christian Religious studies since it is not a compulsory subject. This reduces the number of students enrolled for both internal and external examination across the country. In addition, this transfers panic on the mind of those in Junior Secondary School (J.S.S) aimed to avoid it in future. The rate at which those who also offered the subject in external examination; the Senior School Certificate Examinations (SSCE) conducted by the West African Examination council (WAEC) and the National Examination Council (NECO) is decreasing yearly basis. This has become a serious challenge to all education stakeholders and Geography. The performances of the students in both examinations have been attributed to different assertions which could either be the mode of teaching, the students' attitude to the subject, lack of qualified teachers and updated materials. Sofowora and Egbedokun (2010) opined that the resultant effect of the aforementioned is that the subject no longer attracts young scholars due to the dull, uninspiring and stereotyped approach being adopted. These problems need to be addressed and treat as a matter of urgency among the teachers, government, stakeholders and concerned individual in order to curb the alarming complaint from the university that most of the students offering geography as a study lacks prerequisite knowledge of the subject while some were just given the course to study simply because they didn't meet up with the courses applied. For the purpose of this study, it focuses on student attitude to Geography and its effects on the academic performances in Dekina Local Government Area of Kogi State, Nigeria.

(Comparative Assessment of Teacher's-Quality-Assurance Technique and Student's-Attitude on ... Kilani, M. O. Et. al. 2025)

Research Questions

- (i) What is the general attitude of the students towards Geography in the secondary school?
- (ii) What is the influence of gender on the views of the teachers?
- (iii) What is the influence of religion on the teachers' view?
- (iv) What is the influence of educational qualification on the teachers' view?

Research Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a correlational research design to examine the relationships between teacher quality assurance techniques, students' attitudes, and academic performance in Geography. The design allowed for the comparative assessment of how these variables interact within the secondary school context in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Population and Sampling

The study population consisted of all Geography teachers in public senior secondary schools across Kogi State. A multi-stage random sampling technique was implemented to select: 20 secondary schools from different educational zones, 100 Geography teachers (5 teachers per selected school). This sampling approach was used in other to ensured representation across various school types.

Instrumentation

Research Instruments employed for this research are Students' Attitude to Geography Questionnaire (SAGQ) with 5-point Likert scale instrument measuring interest, perception and motivation. This demonstrated reliability ($\alpha = 0.78$) while Teacher Quality Assessment (TQA) evaluated qualifications, teaching methods and professional development which showed strong reliability ($\alpha = 0.82$)

Presentation of Results and Discussions

This section describes the personal information of the teacher (respondents) for the study. It shows the frequency distribution count and the percentage of the respondent based on gender, religion as well as teacher's qualification.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of the Study Sample on the Basis of Gender

Gender	No	Percentage (%)
Male	60	60
Female	40	40
Total	100	100

Author's Analysis, 2024

Table 1 reveals that 60% of geography teachers in the senior secondary schools of the area were male while 40% of the teachers were female. From the analysis, the number of male teachers teaching geography as a subject are more than female teachers with a wide range of 20%. This could lead to low-active participation of female students with the view that, geography is usually for male students.

(Comparative Assessment of Teacher's-Quality-Assurance Technique and Student's-Attitude on ... Kilani, M. O. Et. al. 2025)

In addition, similar scenarios can also be found in most of Nigerian tertiary institution (Colleges of Education and University). However, this disagrees with the results of Onuoha and Eze (2014) students' attitude towards the study of geography in Nsukka Local Government Area, Enugu State, Nigeria and found out that Female performances in geography outnumbered male student with 107 against 93.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution on the Basis of Religion

Religion	Number	Percentage
Christian	50	50
Muslim	50	50
Total	100	100

Author's Analysis, 2024

Table 2 reveals that 50% of the teachers are Christian while on the other hand 50% of the teachers are Muslim. This shows that there are no any disparities between Muslim and Christian among the teachers. In addition to the above results, the effect of religion on the attitude of students to geography and its academic performance shows neutral.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution on the Basis of Teachers' Qualification

Qualification	Number	Percentage
Qualified	56	56
Unqualified	44	44
Total	100	100

Author's Analysis, 2024

Table 3 shows the qualification of the respondents in teaching Geography. The table revealed that out of 100 questionnaires distributed across the selected senior secondary school, it was observed that 56% of the respondents are qualified professionally to teach the subject by having M.Ed., B.Sc. Ed, B.A.Ed. and NCE respectively while 44% are unqualified to teach the subject because they are not trained to teach the students. However, this does not affect the general performance of the students in the study area. This could be as a result of consistency in teaching geography and mastery of the subject matter for the betterment of the students.

Presentation of Result

Research Question 1: What is the general attitude of students towards geography in secondary school?

Table 5: The Mean Score of Attitude of Students towards Academic Performance

Highest score	Lowest score	Mean score	Frequency
58	-16	1594	
Total			100

Author's Analysis, 2024

(Comparative Assessment of Teacher's-Quality-Assurance Technique and Student's-Attitude on ... Kilani, M. O. Et. al. 2025)

From table 5., the calculated highest score of the student's attitude to Geography was 58 and the lowest score was -16 with the total mean score of the respondents 1594. This reveals that the attitude of the respondents towards geography as a school subjects and students' academic performance was generally positive. This corroborated with the results of Tomal, 2010 who found that geography is ranked fourth among the most favorable courses. However, the students 'positive opinion about their teachers was the most effective factor that increase students' interest in the lesson.

Research question 2: What is the influence of gender on the view of the respondents?

This section describes the correlation analysis of the relationship between the view of male and female teachers.

Table 6: The Influence of Gender on the view of the Respondents

N	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY	R	Interpretation
100	662	686	19,802	23,688	5,664	-18.8	Negative relationship

Author's Analysis, 2024

Table 6 revealed that the r = -18.8, this shows that there was a negative relationship between the views of male and female teachers about the influence on the academic performance of the students.

Research question 3: What is the influence of Religion on the view of the respondents?

This table shows the correlation analysis of the relationship between the view of Christian and Muslim teachers on the students' attitude to Geography.

Table 7: The Influence of Religion on the view of the Respondents

N	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY	R	interpretation
100	992	586	22,992	21,132	11,688	0.41	Moderate relationship

Author's Analysis, 2024

Table 7 indicates the calculated value as 0.41. This show that there was a moderate relationship between the views of the respondents on the basis of their religion. Religion has no effects on students' academic performance whether Muslim or Christian.

(Comparative Assessment of Teacher's -Quality-Assurance Technique and Student's -Attitude on ... Kilani, M. O. Et. al. 2025)

Research question 4. What is the influence of Teacher qualification on the view of the respondent?

Table 8: The Influence of Teacher Qualification on the view of the Respondent

N	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY	R	Interpretation
100	954	432	29,722	15,196	14,812	0.64	Substantial relationship

Author's Analysis, 2024

Table 8 revealed the relationship co-efficient of correlation of views on the basis of the qualification. This shows that $r = 0.64$. There was a substantial correlation between the views of the experienced (qualified and unqualified) teacher on the academic performance of the students in Geography.

Summary of the Findings

- i. It was observed that there was a positive relationship on the general attitude of students to Geography and their academic performance in Dekina LGA. That is to say the view of respondents on the attitude of students to Geography and its effect on academic performance was generally positive, this is because teachers have a direct influence on the students' academic performance.
- ii. The result further revealed that there is a negative correlation between the views of male and female teachers supported by a low result gotten from gender of the teachers, where female teacher of Geography was lower than that of the male teacher.
- iii. More so, the result revealed a moderate relationship on the views of the respondents on the basis of their religion. This was supported by the scores gotten from the Christian (50%) and Muslim (50%) which means there is no difference.
- iv. Lastly, the view on qualification revealed a substantial relationship. The result shows that (56%) of Geography teachers were highly qualified more than non-qualified (44%).

Recommendations

Based on the finding, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The teachers should continue doing better and update their methodology where necessary for them to meet up with the current trends in maintaining positive attitude of their students towards Geography.
- ii. There should be efficient counselling, awareness in senior secondary schools by the stakeholders, geography bodies, government and individuals to call for more participation in geography by the student and females are not exempted.
- iii. Geography teachers with NCE should be given full training (i.e. in-services training) so they can improve their performance and those that are not qualify by profession should be encourage to go further for the degree in Geography.
- iv. Parents should think outside the box by encouraging their wards to see the importance of Geography in life and allow them to offer it from their senior secondary level to the higher institution.

(*Comparative Assessment of Teacher's -Quality-Assurance Technique and Student's -Attitude on ... Kilani, M. O. Et. al. 2025*)

- v. Government should make Geography as a compulsory subject for the senior secondary school students and seminars, workshops and symposium should be organized periodically for new method of teaching the subject.

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